

The Darkness Beholds: (Re)Membering, (Re)Visiting and (Re)Turning to the Self and the City in Sunetra Gupta's *Memories of Rain*

Samra Ejaz

M.A. English, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi
samra8271@gmail.com

Abstract:

The promiscuous gaze of West ever penetrates the “exotic” East, wanting to possess and dominate every part of it indiscriminately. The fascination for its dark secrets arises a momentary pleasure within the Occidental which ebbs once the need to possess the inexplicable is fed. In Sunetra Gupta’s novel, Memories of Rain, Anthony, from London, characterises as a neo-Orientalist who fetishizes Bengal and feminises the nation out of his deep desire to penetrate within its darkness. However, elusive Bengal causes him to be enthralled by Moni, a middle-class Bengali woman whose unyielding silence makes her a body metaphor of the city. When Anthony, her deceitful husband, finally possesses Moni and takes her with him to London after marriage, the gendered dichotomies of colonialist and heterosexual desire operating in the novel find new roots in Moni’s psychological disintegration and her shattered diasporic self. Having so far existed within her husband’s essentialized construction of her identity within the space of diaspora, Moni who shares an unresolved relationship, or “darkness” with Bengal, begins to harbour a nostalgia for her originary home. As her abandoned lover, Calcutta, claims her back, Moni remembers and revisits her memories of the city, and with Anthony, to reevaluate her identity inextricably attached to her homeland, and her idealised version of London. Moni’s selfhood is hence reclaimed in her final return to Calcutta, now a Third Space - because of her constant revision and selective appropriation of the city through her memories. In her reimagination, Calcutta emerges as ambivalent while her migrant identity itself emerges as amorphous (Ahmed 342). Thus, this paper discusses how this postcolonial autobiographical novel uses the narrative of double consciousness, fractured memory and chronotope to deliver its protagonist to a Third Space, a space unbounded by dichotomies and identity. Through discourse analysis, this paper also studies how Gupta’s poetic prose enables Moni’s deliberate performance of (re)imagination - essentially leaving image-clusters peculiar to the modern life and ethos of the middle-class Calcutta Bengalis from the 1960s and 1970s.

Keywords: Indian Diaspora, Calcutta, Identity, Memory, Culture

“Displacement” as a process comes to relate both with diaspora and memory for not only there’s an actual displacement in space taking place, but memory, understood as “an active process by which meanings are created” (Portelli, 2018, p. 240), prospers on imagination wherein one idea is substituted by another related idea. Diasporic individuals entangled in the politics of remembering and forgetting, ‘here’ and ‘there’, often construct their diasporic identity within the realm of the memory of a distant place of birth and origins, or imaginary “home” (Safran, 1991, p. 83). These memories, nostalgically evoked as an antidote to the clamour of the present, are fluid, temporal and unstable so as to disallow any secure “ground” for identity (Fortier, 2000). Hence, their unreliability or “rootlessness” is itself acknowledged as a derivative of a displaced subject. Winner of the Sahitya Academy Award for the year 1996, Sunetra Gupta’s debut novel *Memories of Rain* (1992) tells the story of a middle-class Bengali woman, Moni who contemplates leaving her deceitful English husband, Anthony - who has an affair with another English woman Anna - to return to Calcutta along with her six-year-old daughter. In Gupta’s novel, Anthony characterises as a neo-Orientalist who fetishizes Bengal and feminises the nation to penetrate deep within its darkness. However, elusive Bengal causes him to be enthralled by Moni whose unyielding silence makes her a body metaphor of the city. When Anthony finally possesses Moni and takes her with him to London after marriage, the gendered dichotomies of colonialist and heterosexual desire operating in the novel find new roots in Moni’s psychological disintegration and her shattered diasporic self. Having so far existed within her husband’s essentialized construction of her subaltern identity within the space of diaspora, Moni who shares an unresolved relationship, or “darkness” with Bengal, begins to harbour a nostalgia for her originary home. Her return to Calcutta is eventually necessitated by the constant visitations to the past and psychological absence in the present which invites a “double-consciousness” or split identity.

The entire novel spans to a single weekend in Moni’s life where her recollections begin from that day in “the flood of ’78” (Gupta, 1992, p. 3) when Anthony had first come to their Ballygunge home in Calcutta, to eventually culminating into image-clusters portraying the modern life and ethos of the middle-class Calcutta Bengalis from the 1960s and 1970s who are tied in an inextricable bond to their homeland. Moni’s fantasies of the affluent West, her idealised version of London - a “demi-paradise” (Gupta, 1992, p. 157) upon which once walked Shakespeare, Dickens, Hardy, Woolf, Keats - was torn asunder when she realises that she was unable to bloom in her new surroundings. Not only was she still a “stranger to this land” (Gupta, 1992, p. 98) holding on steadfastly to her Indian way of life but Anthony's silent rejection of her presence also echoed in the city’s reproachment of her: “she had wanted to make this her home, and instead the city had remained stately and aloof, the dispassionate streets look upon her now, silent, ignoring the secret they share...” (Gupta, 1992, p. 81). Besides, although Moni’s western education enabled her to realise the dream of “wandering as a spirit with her beloved upon English moors” (Gupta, 1992, p. 177), her half-opinionated conversations and inadequate articulations signified only passive assimilation with their culture. Believing that by marrying Anthony she was saved from a “sterile existence” (Gupta, 1992, p. 45) on a bizarre land (India) where “... they still burn their wives, bury alive their female children?” (Gupta,

1992, p. 6), her nostalgia initially emphasised on the negative aspect of her past: “when all of Calcutta was one large sea of mud and dung, and floating waterlogged Ambassador cars, and children disappeared on their way home from school into open manholes, their covers wrenched off and sold long ago, to drown in the city’s choked sewers...” (Gupta, 1992, p. 5). However, as the illusion of marital bliss withers and she discovers her identity inseparable from her homeland, her nostalgic memory would increasingly evoke its positive attributes to provide a liberating potential; moulding her imagination from a liminal space into a space of rebellion which not only permits a better understanding of her past that may not have been originally possible, but also allows a freedom from the coercive patterns of patriarchal control and from the disillusionment of the present:

and yet, ten years ago, every alleyway in Ballygunge had trembled with the heaviness of her departure, weeping puddles upon the cracked pavements, they had turned away, indignant, betrayed, she will go back to them, the narrow pitted streets, cloaked in a miasma of car fumes, the dung smoke of a thousand clay ovens. (Gupta, 1992, p. 81)

In *Acts of Memory*, Leo Spitzer (1999) underscores the political dimension of the nostalgic memory and calls it critical nostalgia. He argues that the critical awareness of one’s positive and negative aspects of the past is not mutually exclusive but rather serves for a complete reconciliation with the disjointed past. While theorists like James Clifford describes diasporic consciousness as being arrested in two different temporalities - one of attachment and the other of lived reality (1994, pp. 312-318), the discussion of Anne-Marie Fortier’s concept of time-space in the context of diasporic memory and living gains here a greater currency (2005). Understanding diaspora chronotopically implies homeland not as a frozen, static location in the past, recoverable by a simple return to it physically, but as a spatio-temporal construct of the “changing same” (Gilroy, 1993) which travels with the ambivalent identity of the diasporic subject itself. Thus, in the novel, Moni’s diasporic identity predicated on the various constructions of time-space encountered and performatively enacted by her, evolves as a continuous becoming to move beyond any given fixity. In fact, even the performance of revisioning her past cannot yield to her a stable source of identity but only invites a new position of reimagining Bengal as a new land: “She is seized by an overwhelming desire to return to that world, although she knows it is there for her no longer...” (Gupta, 1992, p. 15). Further, the memories of incessant rain that falls in Calcutta becomes another pertinent referent to a time-space of the home which is no more but from which Moni derives her recuperative spirit by the deliberate performance of recollection and longing:

... a land where the rain poured from the skies not to purify the earth, but to spite it, to churn the parched fields into festering wounds, rinse the choked city sewers onto the streets, sprinkle the pillows with the nausea of mould, and yet the poet had pleaded with the deep green shadows of the rain clouds not to abandon him... (Gupta, 1992, p. 6-7)

Anne-Marie Fortier also posits how leaving the homeland does not necessitate a complete loss of its ethos since multiple places may share the same organising chronotope. In other words, the traditions of home chronotope can be effectively re-enacted or “re-membered” in the host chronotope through the creation of “habitual spaces,” where habit and memory carry a temporal vitality (2000, p. 47). As a result, Moni also rebuilds the familiarity of her homeland through reflecting on the affective associations with her friends and family which earlier hadn’t impressed upon her consciousness:

From time to time she had looked at her watch whose hands still marked the time of a world she had left behind, it was six in the morning in Calcutta, her father would be stretching his limbs in preparation for his journey to the market, her mother wiping the night sweat from her brow with a stale sari...her grandmother has been up since four, she has bathed and prayed at her small household shrine, she will touch the blessed flowers to their foreheads, her brother, asleep in her bed, will stir in his sleep as the wet petals graze his skin. (Gupta, 1992, p. 104)

Nevertheless, I argue that it is only at the resolution of making a physical return, and not in mnemonic deliverance, to a reimagined city that Moni learns to re-evaluate her identity against the space of diaspora. On the one hand, she comes to recognize the incompatibility of the binary oppositions that govern her life and make her alien in the foreign land. On the other hand, through revisiting the irrevocable past of unreal Calcutta, she constructs a new time-space which further decentres her consciousness. So, when Moni breaks her favourite blue bowl, it is “her first concrete recognition of approaching disaster, her first rebellion” (Gupta, 1992, p. 94) towards claiming an agency. In continuity, Moni’s final attempt to salvage her identity is articulated in the creation of a Third Space wherein every operative binaries present in her life collapse. Her return to Calcutta marks the initiation of an ambivalent space, devoid of any East-West binary, or ‘here’ and ‘there’ divide. Such cultural articulation and interpretation defining a destabilised diasporic identity is rightly expressed by Bhabha in his concept of Third Space:

The intervention of the Third Space, which makes the structure of meaning and reference an ambivalent process, destroys this mirror of representation in which cultural knowledge is continuously revealed as an integrated, open, expanding code...the disruptive temporality of enunciation displaces the narrative of the western. (Bhabha, 1995/2024, p. 206)

In the introduction to their collection *Migrants of Identity*, Nigel Rapport and Andrew Dawson comment that it shall remain a paradox whether the movement of diasporic communities towards home is linear or circular (1998). Seen through the lens of the chronotope, these diaspora communities, despite their own, sometimes rigid, determinations of who they are, end up embodying views of identity as a process of constant movement in time, space, and timespace (Pereen, 2006). In view of this light, the protagonist of Gupta's novel, makes a circular journey towards home, not just in imagination, but in the real time-space of Calcutta.

This paper, hence, criticises contemporary discourse of diaspora studies that finds the metaphor of memory as an alternative “ground” of identity and rejects the reversal of diaspora teleology as implausible. It also seeks to investigate the dichotomies of colonialist and heterosexual desire that incites Moni’s rejection of the host chronotope, having thence already established how the inversion of the teleology of diaspora in the novel fortifies her attempt to re-define and re-create who she is, perhaps, a new beginning which opens her to an agential future:

When she goes back, she can work for a charity, expunge her sins of having lived in a land of plenty by devoting her life to the poor, the diseased, the hungry...that is how she will spend the rest of her life...She will give her life to the city that she left behind, so many years ago, before its wooing of her was complete, she had crept away, before she might have shared the deathly pain of dying desire with its forlorn streets. (Gupta, 1992, pp. 108-109)

In the novel, Moni, the protagonist presents a hallowed understanding of femininity. She views the “absence of a man’s touch” (Gupta, 1992, p. 147) over a female’s body with great insecurity - as a forlorn, decayed, decrepit state of being. The promise of Anthony’s passionate love, or a deceitful lust, validates that interpretation of her femininity which has been enforced upon her by the dominant. As a student of Bengali theatre who had come to India, Anthony is fascinated by Moni, who represents to him the “darkness” of this tropical land, and so he conceives her as an orientalist project of sorts. He essentialises her whole being to an exotic East meant to be unveiled, possessed, penetrated and conquered. But while the alienness of Bengal eludes and frustrates him, the ungraspable differences between their worlds only propel him to grow relentless in his pursuit of marrying her: “he felt utterly excluded, he was an alien, and suddenly he was no longer content to be a detached observer, the gentle anthropologist, it was a role that had become bitter to him” (Gupta, 1992, p. 38). The naked desire to possess India and Moni plagues his imagination for he himself cannot yield to the domination of a deafening, tropical ‘silence’: “He had come to this land, as his forefathers had done, with a conviction that all he wanted would be his, he had not come with greed, only a desire for knowledge, for experience, and he had known that these would be there for him” (Gupta, 1992, p. 40). Consequently, Anthony’s orientalist perspective and sense of entitlement reduces Moni to the Other - to a “dying bird he has catapulted down” or “an abandoned pet” (Gupta, 1992, p. 46) which commands no more a parallel subjectivity. Both the gender and colonial oppression reinforces her subaltern status for either her coveted silence is fetishized as a deep tropical silence of the East, or her voice is effectively silenced by the dominant discourses which invisibilise her identity: “I have never known her to be so voluble, never...for she had unleashed an exotic aroma, suddenly from within her, strange myths, and violet memories, hothouse flowers” (Gupta, 1992, p. 121). Through the blatant sexualisation of Moni’s body, Anthony’s colonial gaze also feminises Calcutta as an “unashamed” woman waiting to be penetrated such that both the land as well as the woman lies victim to his lust and masculine rape fantasies:

for he felt on that day that he had penetrated the very spirit of life in this city, the very essence of their culture had been revealed to him in the few dense hours

he had gazed upon the rain-swollen curve of her mouth, this was what he had come to discover, to feel, the inebriation of tropical rain upon his skin, the sensual exchange of poetry on a thunderous evening, oh, if he could only draw his lips through the velvet valley of her hair, his experience of the tropics would be complete, if he could only once graze the succulence of her lips. (Gupta, 1992, p. 124)

Hence, so far betrayed by Anthony's spent passion of lust, the disjuncture between Moni's nostalgic past and bruised present suspends her between two temporalities. On the one hand, London, like Anthony, refuses to acknowledge her full presence, on the other hand, Calcutta, yearning for her return, stands as a betrayed and devastated lover. Moni's tryst with darkness becomes another important trope in the novel that comes to define a tripartite relationship between Calcutta, herself, and her dissociated self within the space of diaspora. Darkness, Moni's childhood companion and true love, silently beholds her, hovering around every time-space she inhabits. It stands as a jealous lover when her relationship with Anthony is consummated (Gupta 1992), but its desperation is finally reciprocated when Moni decides to reject London and re-embrace Calcutta in a re-imagined way. Thus, darkness evolves as the metaphoric signifier of her problematic and unresolved relationship with the city: "she fancies it is darkness, her old lover, enfolding her once again in a graceful lust, the gentle sweep of incorporeal desire" (Gupta, 1992, p. 189). Moni, who ten years ago could not share her love with Calcutta (Gupta, 1992), now re-configures her gender ambiguously as she metaphorically engages in a masculine act of penetration by "returning", or rather "(re)entering" the city. In her theorization of migration, Sara Ahmed posits that migration is felt at the level of embodiment and bodies (re)inhabit space in their quest for homes. She claims that "[w]hat migration narratives involve, then, is a spatial reconfiguration of an embodied self: a transformation of the very skin through which the body is embodied" (Ahmed, 1999, p. 342). While Calcutta appears to be feminised in Gupta's narrative, the gender of both darkness and Moni appears amorphous which eventually disrupts the heteronormative, gendered binaries established earlier in the novel. It is no surprise then that while Sunetra Gupta subscribes to the Saidian framework of Orientalism for her protagonist, much to the chagrin of contemporary feminist discourse, Moni in reversing the teleology of diaspora and rejecting the governing binaries of her life, in fact, moves away from any sorts of essentialization. Thus, she rejects her female body as the only source of her identity and seeks to move beyond any given fixity that restrains her autonomy. Just as a tropical darkness unable to be encompassed and tamed, engulfing time and space with its boundlessness, the end of the novel gives a notion of fluidity to Moni's identity as she comes to reinhabit Calcutta as a Third space. In somewhat ironical reality of an immigrant life, what forecloses the possibility of her return were the same shards of images that once drove her away from her homeland, perhaps, without the exilic space of London, she wouldn't have been able to behold her 'darkness' from an intimate distance.

Author's Bio-note

Samra Ejaz (she/her) has recently completed her M.A. in English from Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi. She has a Bachelor's degree in English literature from Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi. Her research interests include Diaspora Studies, Memory and Trauma Studies, and Human Rights and Literature.

email ID- samra8271@gmail.com

Contact - 8002568872

References

- [1] Ahmed, S. (1999). Home and away: Narratives of migration and estrangement. *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 2(3), 329-347. <https://doi.org/10.1177/136787799900200303>
- [2] Bhabha, H. (2024). Cultural Diversity and Cultural Differences. *The Post-Colonial Studies Reader*. Ed. Bill Ashcroft, Gareth Griffiths and Helen Tiffin (3rd ed.). Routledge, 206-12. (Original work published in 1995). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429469039>
- [3] Clifford, J. (1994). Diasporas. *Cultural Anthropology*, 9(3), 302-338. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/656365>
- [4] Dawson, A., & Rapport, N. (Eds.). (1998). *Migrants of Identity: Perceptions of 'Home' in a World of Movement* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003136149>
- [5] Fortier, A.M. (2000). *Migrant Belongings: Memory, Space, Identity* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003086093>
- [6] Fortier, A.M. (2005). Diaspora. *Cultural Geography. A Critical Dictionary of Key Concepts*. Eds. David Atkinson et al. London, New York: I.B. Tauris, 182-87.
- [7] Gilroy, P. (1993). *The Black Atlantic : Modernity and double consciousness*. Cambridge, Mass : Harvard University Press.
- [8] Gupta, S. (1992). *Memories of Rain*. New York: Grove Weidenfeld.
- [9] Peeren, E. (2006). Through the Lens of the Chronotope: Suggestions for a Spatio-Temporal Perspective on Diaspora. In *Diaspora and Memory*. Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill, 13, 67-78. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789401203807_007
- [10] Portelli, A. (2018). Living Voices: The oral history interview as dialogue and experience. *The Oral History Review*, 45(2), 239-248. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ohr/ohy030>
- [11] Safran, W. (1991). Diasporas in Modern Societies: Myths of homeland and return. *Diaspora: A Journal of Transnational Studies*, 1, 83 - 99.
- [12] Spitzer, L., Crewe, J. V., & Bal, M. (1999). *Acts of Memory : Cultural Recall in the Present*. Hanover: Dartmouth college.